

On perserving neutrosophic g -closed sets

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Abstract. In this paper we extend the concepts of a -closed and a -continuous mappings to neutrosophic topological spaces and obtain several results concerning the preservation of neutrosophic g -closed sets. Further more we characterize neutrosophic $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -spaces in terms of neutrosophic a -continuous and neutrosophic a -closed mappings and obtain some of the basic properties and characterization of these mappings.

Keywords: Neutrosophic g -closed sets; neutrosophic g -open sets; neutrosophic g -continuous; neutrosophic g -irresolute; neutrosophic a -closed and neutrosophic a -continuous mappings.

1. Introduction

In 1965, Zadeh [24] introduced the notion of fuzzy sets. Later, fuzzy topological space was introduced by Chang [5] in 1968 using fuzzy sets. In 1986, Atanassov [4] introduced the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy sets, where the degree of membership and degree of non-membership of an element in a set X are discussed. In 1997, Intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces were introduced by Coker [6] using intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Neutrality the degree of indeterminacy as an independent concept was introduced by Florentine Smarandache [21]. He [21] defined neutrosophic set on a non empty set by considering three components, namely membership, Indeterminacy and non-membership whose sum lies between 0 and 3. Some more properties of neutrosophic sets are presented by Smarandache [21–23], Salama and Alblowi [18], Lupiáñez [13]. Smarandache's Neutrosophic concepts have wide range of real time applications for the fields of Information systems, Computer science, Artificial Intelligence, Applied Mathematics and Decision making. In 2008, Lupiáñez [13] introduced the neutrosophic

topology as an extension of intuitionistic fuzzy topology. Since 2008 many authors such as Lupiáñez [13,14], Salama et.al. [18,19] Karatas and Cemil [11], Acikgoz and his coworkers [1,2], Dhavaseelan et.al. [7–9], Parimala et.al. [16], Al-Omeri and Jafari [3], and others extended various topological notions to neutrosophic sets and studied in neutrosophic topological spaces. In 1970, Levine [12] introduced the concept of g -closed sets, which play a very important role in general topology and they are now the research topics of many researchers worldwide. In 2018 [8] extended g -closed sets in neutrosophic topology. Recently many authors such as Salmaa [19], Jayanti [10], Al-Omeri and Jafari [3], Mohammed Ali Jaffer and Ramesh [15], Parimala et.al. [16,17] and others studies neutrosophic g -closed sets and their weak forms in neutrosophic topological spaces. In this paper we introduce the concepts of neutrosophic a - closed and neutrosophic a -continuous mappings using neutrosophic g - closed sets. These definitions enable us to obtain conditions under which maps and inverse maps preserve neutrosophic g - closed sets [9] . We also characterize neutrosophic $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -spaces in terms of neutrosophic a -continuous and neutrosophic a - closed mappings. Finally some of basic properties of neutrosophic a - continuous and neutrosophic a - closed mappings are investigated.

2. Preliminaries

Since we shall require the following known definitions, notations and some properties, we recall them in this section.

Definition 2.1. [21] A Neutrosophic set (**NS**) in X is a structure

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \varpi_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

where $\mu_A : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$, $\varpi_A : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$, and $\gamma_A : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ denotes the membership, indeterminacy, and non-membership of A satisfies the condition if $-0 \leq \mu_A(x) + \varpi_A(x) + \gamma_A(x) \leq 3^+$, $\forall x \in X$.

In the real life applications in scientific and engineering problems it is difficult to use neutrosophic set with value from real standard or non-standard subset of $] -0, 1^+[$. Hence we consider the neutrosophic set which takes the value from the closed interval $[0,1]$ and sum of membership, indeterminacy, and non-membership degrees of each element of universe of discourse lies between 0 and 3. The family of all **NS**s over X will be denoted by $\mathbf{N}(X)$.

Definition 2.2. [20] Let X be a non empty set and the neutrosophic sets A and neutrosophic set B be in the form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \varpi_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$, $B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \varpi_B(x), \gamma_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ and let $\{A_i : i \in J\}$ be an arbitrary family of neutrosophic sets in X . Then:

- (a) $A \subseteq B$ if $\mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x)$, $\varpi_A(x) \leq \varpi_B(x)$, and $\gamma_A(x) \geq \gamma_B(x)$.

- (b) $A = B$ if $A \subseteq B$ and $B \subseteq A$.
- (c) $A^c = \{ \langle x, \gamma_A(x), \varpi_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$.
- (d) $\cap A_i = \{ \langle x, \wedge \mu_{A_i}(x), \wedge \varpi_{A_i}(x), \vee \gamma_{A_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$.
- (e) $\cup A_i = \{ \langle x, \vee \mu_{A_i}(x), \vee \varpi_{A_i}(x), \wedge \gamma_{A_i}(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$.
- (f) $\tilde{\mathbf{0}} = \{ \langle x, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{1}} = \{ \langle x, 1, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$

Definition 2.3. [13, 18] A neutrosophic topology on a non empty set X is a family τ of neutrosophic sets in X , satisfying the following axioms:

- (T₁) $\tilde{\mathbf{0}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{1}} \in \tau$
- (T₂) $G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau$
- (T₃) $G_1 \cup G_2 \in \tau$

In this case the pair (X, τ) is called a neutrosophic topological space and each neutrosophic set in τ is known as a neutrosophic open set in X . The complement A^c of a neutrosophic open set A is called a neutrosophic closed set in X .

Definition 2.4. [18] Let (X, τ) be a neutrosophic topological space and A be a neutrosophic set in X . Then the neutrosophic interior and neutrosophic closure of A are defined by:

$$\text{Cl}(A) = \cap \{K: K \text{ is a neutrosophic closed set such that } A \subseteq K \}$$

$$\text{Int}(A) = \cup \{K: K \text{ is a neutrosophic open set such that } K \subseteq A \}$$

Definition 2.5. [8, 19] A neutrosophic set A of a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) is called:

- (a) neutrosophic g - closed if $\text{Cl}(A) \subseteq O$ whenever $A \subseteq O$ and O is neutrosophic open.
- (b) neutrosophic g - open if and only if A^c is neutrosophic g - closed.

Remark 2.6. [8, 19] Every neutrosophic closed set is neutrosophic g - closed but its converse may not be true.

Remark 2.7. [8, 19] Every neutrosophic open set is neutrosophic g - open but its converse may not be true.

Theorem 2.8. [8, 19] A neutrosophic set A of a neutrosophic topological space is neutrosophic g -open if and only if $F \subseteq \text{Int}(A)$ whenever F is neutrosophic closed and $F \subseteq A$.

Theorem 2.9. [19] Let (X, τ) be a neutrosophic topological space and Ω be the family of all neutrosophic closed sets of X . Then $\Omega = \tau$ if and only if every neutrosophic set of X is neutrosophic g -closed.

Definition 2.10. [3] A neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) is said to be neutrosophic $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space if every neutrosophic g - closed set in X is neutrosophic closed in X .

Definition 2.11. [1] Consider that f is a mapping from X to Y .

- (a) Let A be a neutrosophic set in X with membership function $\mu_A(x)$, indeterminacy function $\varpi_A(x)$ and non-membership function $\sigma_A(x)$. The image of A under f , written as $f(A)$, is a neutrosophic set of Y whose membership function, indeterminacy function and non-membership function are defined as

$$\mu_{f(A)}(y) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x \in f^{-1}(y)} \{\mu_A(x)\}, & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) \neq \phi, \\ 0, & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) = \phi, \end{cases}$$

$$\varpi_{f(A)}(y) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x \in f^{-1}(y)} \{\varpi_A(x)\}, & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) \neq \phi, \\ 0, & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) = \phi, \end{cases}$$

$$\gamma_{f(A)}(y) = \begin{cases} \inf_{x \in f^{-1}(y)} \{\gamma_A(x)\}, & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) \neq \phi, \\ 0, & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) = \phi, \end{cases}$$

$\forall y \in Y$. Where $f^{-1}(y) = \{x : f(x) = y\}$.

- (b) Let B be a neutrosophic set in Y with membership function $\mu_B(y)$, indeterminacy function $\varpi_B(y)$ and non-membership function $\gamma_B(y)$. Then, the inverse image of B under f , written as $f^{-1}(B)$ is a neutrosophic set of X whose membership function, indeterminacy function and non-membership function are respectively defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{f^{-1}(B)}(x) &= \mu_B(f(x)), \\ \varpi_{f^{-1}(B)}(x) &= \varpi_B(f(x)), \\ \gamma_{f^{-1}(B)}(x) &= \gamma_B(f(x)). \end{aligned}$$

$\forall x \in X$.

Definition 2.12. Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two neutrosophic topological spaces and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a mapping. Then f is said to be:

- (a). neutrosophic continuous [18] if the pre image of each neutrosophic open set of Y is a neutrosophic open set in X .
- (b). neutrosophic g -continuous [8, 19] if the pre image of every neutrosophic closed set in Y is a neutrosophic g -closed set in X .
- (c). neutrosophic g -irresolute [8] if the pre image of every neutrosophic g -closed set in Y is a neutrosophic g -closed set in X .
- (d). neutrosophic closed [8, 19] if the image of each neutrosophic closed set in X is a neutrosophic closed set in Y .

(e). neutrosophic open [8, 19] if the image of each neutrosophic open set of X is a neutrosophic open set in Y .

Remark 2.13. [8, 19] Every neutrosophic continuous mapping is neutrosophic g - continuous, but the converse may not be true.

Remark 2.14. [8] Every neutrosophic g - irresolute mapping is neutrosophic g - continuous, but the converse may not be true. The concepts of neutrosophic g - irresolute and neutrosophic continuous mapping are independent.

3. Neutrosophic a -Closed and neutrosophic a -continuous mappings

Definition 3.1. A mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is said to be neutrosophic a - closed provided that $f(F) \subseteq \text{Int}(A)$ whenever F is a neutrosophic closed set in X , A is a neutrosophic g - open set in Y and $f(F) \subseteq A$.

Theorem 3.2. *Every neutrosophic closed mapping is neutrosophic a - closed.*

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a neutrosophic closed mapping. Let F be neutrosophic closed set in X and A is a neutrosophic g - open set in Y such that $f(F) \subseteq A$. Since f is neutrosophic closed mapping, $f(A)$ is neutrosophic closed set in Y . Now A is neutrosophic g - open and $f(F) \subseteq A \Rightarrow f(F) \subseteq \text{Int}(A)$. Hence f is neutrosophic a -closed. \square

Remark 3.3. The converse of Theorem 3.2 may not be true.

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $U = \{ \langle a, 0.6, 0.5, 0.3 \rangle, \langle b, 0.3, 0.5, 0.6 \rangle \}$ be a neutrosophic set on X . Let $\tau = \{ \tilde{\mathbf{0}}, U, \tilde{\mathbf{1}} \}$ be neutrosophic topology on X . Then the mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (X, \tau)$ defined by $f(a) = b$ and $f(b) = a$ is neutrosophic a - closed but it is not neutrosophic closed.

Definition 3.5. A mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is said to be neutrosophic a - continuous provided that $Cl(F) \subseteq f^{-1}(O)$ whenever F is neutrosophic g -closed set in X , O is a neutrosophic open set in Y and $F \subseteq f^{-1}(O)$.

Theorem 3.6. *Every neutrosophic continuous mapping is neutrosophic a - continuous.*

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a neutrosophic continuous mapping. Let O be a neutrosophic open set of Y and F is a neutrosophic g - closed set of X such that $F \subseteq f^{-1}(O)$. Now since f is neutrosophic continuous, $f^{-1}(O)$ is neutrosophic open set in X . Since F is neutrosophic g - closed and $F \subseteq f^{-1}(O) \Rightarrow Cl(F) \subseteq f^{-1}(O)$. Hence f is neutrosophic a - continuous. \square

Remark 3.7. The converse of Theorem 3.6 may not be true.

Example 3.8. Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $U = \{\langle a, 0.5, 0.5, 0.4 \rangle, \langle b, 0.4, 0.5, 0.5 \rangle\}$ be a neutrosophic set on X . Let $\tau = \{\tilde{\mathbf{0}}, U, \tilde{\mathbf{1}}\}$ be a neutrosophic topology on X . Then the mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (X, \tau)$ defined by $f(a) = b$ and $f(b) = a$ is neutrosophic a -continuous but it is not neutrosophic continuous.

Theorem 3.9. *If $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is a bijection, then f is neutrosophic a -closed if and only if f^{-1} is neutrosophic a -continuous.*

Proof. Obvious. \square

4. Preserving neutrosophic g -closed sets

In this section the concepts of neutrosophic a -continuous and neutrosophic a -closed mappings are used to obtain some results on preservation of neutrosophic g -closed sets.

Theorem 4.1. *If a mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic g -continuous and neutrosophic a -closed then $f^{-1}(A)$ is a neutrosophic g -closed set in X whenever A is a neutrosophic g -closed set in Y .*

Proof. Suppose that $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic g -continuous and neutrosophic a -closed. Let A be a neutrosophic g -closed set in Y such that $f^{-1}(A) \subseteq O$, where O is neutrosophic open set in X . Then $O^c \subseteq f^{-1}(A^c)$ which implies that $f(O^c) \subseteq \text{Int}(A^c) = (\text{Cl}(A))^c$. Hence $f^{-1}(\text{Cl}(A)) \subseteq O$. Since f is neutrosophic g -continuous and $f^{-1}(\text{Cl}(A))$ is neutrosophic g -closed in X , therefore $\text{Cl}(f^{-1}(\text{Cl}(A))) \subseteq O$ which implies that $\text{Cl}(f^{-1}(A)) \subseteq O$. Hence $f^{-1}(A)$ is neutrosophic g -closed set in X . \square

Corollary 4.2. *If a mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic continuous and neutrosophic a -closed then $f^{-1}(A)$ is a neutrosophic g -closed set in X whenever A is a neutrosophic g -closed set in Y .*

Corollary 4.3. *If a mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic continuous and neutrosophic closed then $f^{-1}(A)$ is a neutrosophic g -closed set in X whenever A is a neutrosophic g -closed set in Y .*

Theorem 4.4. *If a mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic g -continuous and neutrosophic a -closed then $f^{-1}(A)$ is neutrosophic g -open set in X whenever A is neutrosophic g -open set in Y .*

Proof. Suppose that $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic g -continuous and neutrosophic a -closed mapping. Let A be neutrosophic g -open in Y . Then by Definition 2.5, A^c is

neutrosophic g - closed in Y . Hence by Theorem 4.1, $f^{-1}(A^c)$ is neutrosophic g - closed in X . Since $f^{-1}(A^c) = (f^{-1}(A))^c$ for every neutrosophic set A of Y , therefore $(f^{-1}(A))^c$ is neutrosophic g -closed set in X . This means that $f^{-1}(A)$ is neutrosophic g - open set in X . \square

Corollary 4.5. *If a mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic continuous and neutrosophic a -closed then $f^{-1}(A)$ is a neutrosophic g -open set in X whenever A is a neutrosophic g - open set in Y .*

Corollary 4.6. *If a mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic continuous and neutrosophic closed then $f^{-1}(A)$ is a neutrosophic g -open set in X whenever A is a neutrosophic g - open set in Y .*

Theorem 4.7. *If $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is a neutrosophic a - continuous and neutrosophic closed mapping then the image of every neutrosophic g - closed set of X is neutrosophic g - closed in Y .*

Proof. Let B be a neutrosophic g - closed set of X , and $f(B) \subseteq O$, where O is a neutrosophic open set in Y . Then $B \subseteq f^{-1}(O)$ and since f is neutrosophic a - continuous, $Cl(B) \subseteq f^{-1}(O)$ which implies that $f(Cl(B)) \subseteq O$. Since f is neutrosophic closed mapping and $Cl(B)$ is neutrosophic closed in X , $f(Cl(B))$ is neutrosophic closed in Y . Thus, we have $Cl(f(B)) \subseteq Cl(f(Cl(B))) = f(Cl(B)) \subseteq O$. Hence $f(B)$ is neutrosophic g - closed in Y . \square

Corollary 4.8. *If $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is a neutrosophic a - continuous and neutrosophic closed mapping then the image of every neutrosophic g - closed set of X is neutrosophic g - closed in Y .*

5. Characterization of neutrosophic $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ - spaces

In the following theorems we give some characterizations of a class of neutrosophic $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -spaces by using the concepts of neutrosophic a - closed and neutrosophic a - continuous mapping.

Theorem 5.1. *A neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) is neutrosophic $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ - space if and only if every mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a - continuous.*

Proof. Necessity: Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ and A is a neutrosophic g -closed set of X and $A \subseteq f^{-1}(O)$ where O is a neutrosophic open set of Y . Since X is a neutrosophic $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ - space, A is neutrosophic closed set in X . Therefore $Cl(A) = A \subseteq f^{-1}(O)$. Hence A is neutrosophic a - continuous.

Sufficiency: Let A be a non empty neutrosophic g - closed set in X and let Y is neutrosophic topological space with the neutrosophic topology $\sigma = \{ \tilde{0}, A, \tilde{1} \}$. Finally let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow$

(Y, σ) be the identity mapping. By assumption f is neutrosophic a - continuous. Since A is neutrosophic g - closed in X and neutrosophic open in Y and $A \subseteq f^{-1}(A)$, it follows that $Cl(A) \subseteq f^{-1}(A) = A$, because f is the identity mapping. Hence A is neutrosophic closed in X and therefore X is a neutrosophic $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ - space. \square

An analogous argument proves the following result for neutrosophic a - closed mapping.

Theorem 5.2. *A neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) is a neutrosophic $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ - space if and only if every mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a - closed.*

6. Properties of Neutrosophic a - closed and neutrosophic a - continuous mappings

In this section we investigate some of the properties of neutrosophic a -closed and neutrosophic a -continuous mappings.

Theorem 6.1. *Every neutrosophic g - continuous and neutrosophic a -closed mapping is neutrosophic g -irresolute.*

Proof. Suppose that $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic g - continuous and neutrosophic a - closed mapping and A is a neutrosophic g - closed set in Y . Let $f^{-1}(A) \subseteq O$ where O is a neutrosophic open set in X . Then $O^c \subseteq f^{-1}(A^c)$ which implies that $f(O^c) \subseteq Int(A^c) = (Cl(A))^c$. Hence $f^{-1}(Cl(A)) \subseteq O$. Since f is neutrosophic g -continuous $f^{-1}(Cl(A))$ is neutrosophic g -closed in X . Therefore $Cl(f^{-1}(Cl(A))) \subseteq O$ which implies that $Cl(f^{-1}(A)) \subseteq O$. Hence $f^{-1}(A)$ is a neutrosophic g -closed set in X . Therefore f is neutrosophic g -irresolute. \square

Corollary 6.2. *Every neutrosophic continuous and neutrosophic a -closed mapping is neutrosophic g -irresolute.*

Theorem 6.3. *If $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is a mapping for which $f(F)$ is neutrosophic open set in Y for every neutrosophic closed set F of X then f is a neutrosophic a - closed mapping.*

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a mapping, F a neutrosophic closed set in X , A a neutrosophic g - open set in Y and $f(F) \subseteq A$. By hypothesis $f(F)$ is neutrosophic open in X . Therefore $f(F) = Int f(F) \subseteq Int(A)$. Hence f is neutrosophic a -closed. \square

Theorem 6.4. *If $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is a mapping for which $f^{-1}(V)$ is neutrosophic closed in X for every neutrosophic open set V of Y , then f is a neutrosophic a -continuous mapping.*

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a mapping. Let F is neutrosophic g -closed set in X and V is neutrosophic open set of Y such that $F \subseteq f^{-1}(V)$. By hypothesis $f^{-1}(V)$ is neutrosophic closed in X . Hence $Cl(f^{-1}(V)) = f^{-1}(V)$. Therefore $Cl(F) \subseteq Cl(f^{-1}(V)) = f^{-1}(V)$. Hence f is neutrosophic a - continuous. \square

Remark 6.5. Since the identity mapping on any neutrosophic topological space is both neutrosophic a - continuous and neutrosophic a - closed, it is clear that the converse of Theorem 6.3 and Theorem 6.4 do not hold.

Theorem 6.6. *If $\sigma = \Upsilon$ where Υ denotes the family of all neutrosophic closed sets of Y , then the mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a - closed if and only if $f(F)$ is a neutrosophic open set in Y , for every neutrosophic closed set F of X .*

Proof. Necessity: Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a - closed mapping. By Theorem 2.9 every neutrosophic set of Y is neutrosophic g - closed and hence all are neutrosophic g - open. Thus for any neutrosophic closed set F of X , $f(F)$ is neutrosophic g - open in Y . Since f is neutrosophic a - closed, $f(F) \subseteq Int(f(F))$ and then $f(F) = Int(f(F))$. Hence $f(F)$ is neutrosophic open.

Sufficiency: Let F be a neutrosophic closed set of X and A be a neutrosophic g - open set of Y and $f(F) \subseteq A$. By hypothesis $f(F)$ is neutrosophic open in Y and $f(F) = Int(f(F)) \subseteq Int(A)$. Hence f is neutrosophic a - closed. \square

Theorem 6.7. *If $\sigma = \Upsilon$ where Υ denotes the family of all neutrosophic closed sets of Y then the mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a - closed if and only if f is neutrosophic closed.*

Proof. Necessity: Let O be a neutrosophic closed set of X . Then by Theorem 6.6 $f(O)$ is neutrosophic open in Y . Since every neutrosophic open set is neutrosophic open, therefore $f(O)$ is neutrosophic open in Y and hence by hypothesis $f(O)$ is neutrosophic closed in Y and therefore $f(O)$ is neutrosophic closed in Y . Hence f is neutrosophic closed.

Sufficiency: Let F be a neutrosophic closed set of X and A be a intuitionistic g -open set of Y and $f(F) \subseteq A$. Since f is neutrosophic closed, $f(F)$ is neutrosophic closed in Y and therefore $(f(F))^c$ is neutrosophic open in Y . By hypothesis $(f(F))^c$ is neutrosophic closed in Y and hence $f(F)$ is neutrosophic open in Y which implies that $f(F) = Int(f(F)) \subseteq Int(A)$. Hence f is neutrosophic a -closed. \square

Theorem 6.8. *If $\tau = \Omega$ where Ω denotes the family of all neutrosophic closed sets of X , then the mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a - continuous if and only if $f^{-1}(O)$ is neutrosophic closed in X for every neutrosophic open set O of Y .*

Proof. Necessity: Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a -continuous mapping. By Theorem 2.9 every neutrosophic set of X is neutrosophic g - closed and hence all are neutrosophic g - open. Thus for any neutrosophic open set O of Y , $f^{-1}(O)$ is neutrosophic g -closed in X . Since $f^{-1}(O) \subseteq f^{-1}(O)$ and f is neutrosophic a -continuous then $Cl(f^{-1}(O)) \subseteq f^{-1}(O)$. Hence $f^{-1}(O)$ is neutrosophic closed set in X .

Sufficiency: Let O be a neutrosophic open set of Y and A be a neutrosophic g -closed set of X such that $A \subseteq f^{-1}(O)$ then $Cl(A) \subseteq Cl(f^{-1}(O)) = f^{-1}(O)$ because by hypothesis $f^{-1}(O)$ is neutrosophic closed in X . Hence f is neutrosophic a -continuous. \square

Theorem 6.9. *If $\tau = \Omega$ where, Ω denotes the family of all neutrosophic closed sets of X , then the mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a -continuous if and only if it is neutrosophic continuous.*

Proof. Necessity: Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a -continuous mapping. Let O is a neutrosophic open set of Y , then by Theorem 6.7 $f^{-1}(O)$ is neutrosophic closed in X and so by hypothesis $f^{-1}(O)$ is neutrosophic open in X . Hence f is neutrosophic continuous.

Sufficiency: Let O be a neutrosophic open set of Y and A be a neutrosophic g -closed set of X such that $A \subseteq f^{-1}(O)$. Since f is neutrosophic continuous, $f^{-1}(O)$ is neutrosophic open in X and thus by hypothesis $f^{-1}(O)$ is neutrosophic pre-closed in X which implies that $Cl(A) \subseteq Cl(f^{-1}(O)) = f^{-1}(O)$. Hence f is neutrosophic a - continuous. \square

Theorem 6.10. *If $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic closed and $g : (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \vartheta)$ is neutrosophic a -closed mapping, then $g \circ f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Z, \vartheta)$ is neutrosophic a -closed.*

Proof. Let F be a neutrosophic closed set of X and A is neutrosophic g - open set of Z for which $g \circ f(F) \subseteq A$. Since $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is a neutrosophic closed mapping , $f(F)$ is a neutrosophic closed set of Y . Now $g : (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \vartheta)$ is neutrosophic a - closed mapping, then $g(f(F)) \subseteq Int(A)$. Hence $g \circ f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Z, \vartheta)$ is neutrosophic a -closed mapping. \square

Theorem 6.11. *If $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a -closed and $g : (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \vartheta)$ is neutrosophic open and neutrosophic g -irresolute then $g \circ f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Z, \vartheta)$ is neutrosophic a - closed.*

Proof. Let F be a neutrosophic closed set of X and A a neutrosophic g -open set of Z for which $gof(F) \subseteq A$. Then $f(F) \subseteq g^{-1}(A)$. Since g is g -irresolute, $g^{-1}(A)$ is neutrosophic g -open in X and $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a -closed mapping. It follows that $f(F) \subseteq Int(g^{-1}(A))$. Thus $(gof)(F) = g(f(F)) \subseteq g(Int(g^{-1}(A))) \subseteq Int(g(g^{-1}(A))) \subseteq Int(A)$. Hence $gof : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Z, \phi)$ is neutrosophic a -closed. \square

Theorem 6.12. *If $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a -continuous and $g : (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \vartheta)$ is neutrosophic continuous then $gof : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Z, \vartheta)$ is neutrosophic a -continuous.*

Proof. Let A be a neutrosophic g -closed set of X and V a neutrosophic open set of Z for which $A \subseteq (gof)^{-1}(V)$. Now since $g : (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \vartheta)$ is neutrosophic continuous, $g^{-1}(V)$ is a neutrosophic open set of Y . Since $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic a -continuous, $Cl(A) \subseteq f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V)) = (gof)^{-1}(V)$. Hence $gof : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Z, \vartheta)$ is a neutrosophic a -continuous mapping. \square

7. Conclusions

We have introduced a -closed and a -continuous mappings in neutrosophic topology. Some basic results related to the preservation of neutrosophic g -closed sets have been established. We also have provided examples where such properties fail to be preserved. Moreover, we obtained some characterizations of neutrosophic $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -spaces and neutrosophic g -continuity in terms of newly defined mappings. The work presented in this paper may be the starting point for new theoretical studies, but can be utilized to study compactness, connectedness, and separation axioms in neutrosophic topological spaces. Therefore, we believe that it will be necessary to carry out more theoretical research to establish a general framework for decision-making, pattern recognition, and data mining applications which will be the aim of our future research works.

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